

The Learning Anxiety of the students in the Context of Basic Education

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Abstract. This study assessed the Anxiety of the learners in times of new normal in education. The researchers used the descriptive research method to gather information about the respondents' demographic profile, level of learners anxiety. The data obtained were analyzed using percentage weighted mean, and chi-square to determine the significant degree of relationship between learners profile and the level of learners anxiety. Finding shows that learners have different anxiety on different subjects. Moreover, data shows that test anxiety was the most dominant cause of learners anxiety. In addition, data showed that test and class anxiety are highly correlated with the grade level. This shows that anxiety occurs in different grade level. To sum-up, findings have shown that there is a need to strengthen the connection between students and teachers in order to provide quality education and prevent the existence of academic anxiety.

Keywords: Learning anxiety, test anxiety, Communication and evaluation anxiety

1. Introduction

Our emotional state has long been known to influence our learning capacities, and while a little nervousness before a test or a big project is typical, when that tension piles up too much, it can impair our capacity to take in, process and retain new information (Seal et al., 2011; Tyng et al., 2017). Anxiety, unfortunately, is on the rise among students, with one survey finding that the percentage of students who report having a mental health condition has more than quadrupled in the previous five years (Stenger, 2018). According to research, when we're stressed, our brains simply stop building new connections (Jensen, 2005; Doyle & Zakrajsek, 2018; Siegel, 2020), resulting in memory loss. This is due to the fact that stress and anxiety trigger the body's fight-or-flight response, causing physiological and psychological changes that improve our capacity to respond to danger when faced with a crisis. If we are stressed, our adrenaline levels will rise, our heart rate and breathing will likely speed up, blood will be rerouted to our limbs, and our body temperature will likely rise as well.

Students' performance and anxiety provides low performance in the core subjects. In order to achieve education's primary aim of eradicating illiteracy from the population, which is critical for personal growth and development, schools and students alike must work together and remain committed. Students and teachers in school may work together to achieve their full potential and

achieve their full potential. To help students reach their educational goals, a teacher who is a molder of their knowledge and wisdom, and a proactive builder of skills and habits, is essential. Students, who are the lifeblood of the educational system, require direction and inspiration if they are to grow up to be useful members of society (Westheimer & Kahne, 2004; Davis, 2006)

Previous research showed that anxiety is one of the most significant determinants of academic achievement. Students who suffer from anxiety disorder have a lethargic attitude toward their academics, as evidenced by a lack of enthusiasm in studying and low performance on tests as well as on homework projects (Vitasari et al., 2010).

Anxiety is a subjective sense of tension, uncertainty, uneasiness, and concern that is related with the arousal of the nervous system (arousal of the sympathetic nervous system) (Spielberger, 1983). A high degree of anxiety makes it difficult for a person to go about their usual life, which includes interfering with their activities and social life. Anxiety is one of the many types of emotional and behavioral problems that can occur (Rachel and Chidsey, 2005). Students who suffer from anxiety disorder have a passive attitude toward their academics, exhibiting signs such as a lack of enthusiasm in studying, poor performance on tests, and poor performance on homework projects. Among students, psychological symptoms of anxiety include feeling nervous before a tutorial class, panicking, going blank during a test, feeling helpless while doing assignments, or showing little interest in a difficult subject, whereas physiological symptoms of anxiety include sweaty palms, a racing heartbeat, shortness of breath, a racing pulse, or an upset stomach (Ruffins, 2007). It has been acknowledged by students and educators alike that university students experience significant levels of anxiety.

Catastrophe theory, which analyzes the link between anxiety and performance in terms of athletic performance, was used to develop the anxiety perspective and academic performance. It is critical to comprehend the idea as well as the impact of worry on one's ability to execute. Physiological anxiety, according to Martin and Robb (2005), has a curvilinear association with performance, but cognitive anxiety has a negative link with performance.

The component of cognitive anxiety that has the greatest impact on performance is apprehension (Ingugiro, 1999; Robb, 2005). Cognitive anxiety, according to Fazez and Hardy (1988), has a positive link with performance when physiological arousal is low, and this is supported by research. According to the findings of the study, students who have a higher degree of anxiety likely to receive poorer grades on their end-of-semester assessment (Hamzah, 2007). Students with high levels of anxiety had lower levels of academic accomplishment among high school students, according to a study done by a researcher to determine the relationship between anxiety and academic achievement in high school (McCraty, 2007). Others have voiced the belief that a high degree of worry will be related with poor academic achievement in school (Luigi et al., 2007, and Sena et al., 2007)

Anxiety leads to lack of self-confidence, low self-esteem and behaviors related to classroom language learning as it degrades the competence of the students to participate class discussion especially in the core subjects. The Department of Education envisions to produce a competitive student, with this at hand, it is believing necessary to assess the students on the basis of determining

their level of anxiety in relation to oral competence so that they could able to compete globally. It is the researcher’s hope to improve the oral competence of the students.

2. Research Methodology

to achieve the purpose of this study, the researcher employed the normative descriptive survey method making use of a questionnaire patterned after a standardized tool measuring the students’ anxiety. the researcher used the purposive and universal sampling technique. this research included the input-process-output approach. the input process. The participants of the study were elementary learners who are officially enrolled for the school year 2020-2021. two different sets of research instruments were utilized in this study in order to determine the level of learning anxiety of the students. it was adapted from the classroom anxiety scale (flcas) adapted from park (2014). A transmittal letter will be prepared and address to the office of the district supervisor, requesting permission to conduct the study as the request will be approved; the researcher will start to distribute questionnaires to the students through their parents. Questionnaires will be retrieved and data will be collated. Data and information with regards to the study will be treated with utmost confidence.

3. Purpose of the Study

This research assessed the learning anxiety of learners in core subjects of identified schools at Talisay Division, City of Talisay. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following queries: what is the level of anxiety of the students and the academic performance of the students and the issues and concerns relating to academic anxiety.

Results and Discussions

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Test Anxiety

Test anxiety	Learners					
	Math		English		Science	
	WM	VD	WM	VD	WM	VD
I am worried about making mistakes in our examination.	4.81	VH	3.63	H	3.29	N
I am usually not at ease during our examination.	4.21	VH	3.82	H	3.61	H
I worry about the consequences of failing our examination.	4.09	VH	3.61	H	3.32	N
I am afraid that my teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make.	4.83	VH	3.43	H	3.92	H
The more I study for a test, the more confused I get.	4.54	VH	3.66	H	3.58	H
Weighted Mean	4.50	VH	3.63	H	3.54	H

Table 1 shows the results in terms of learner’s anxiety in terms of test anxiety. Data shows that learners have also a higher anxiety in math classes compared to English and science subjects. Overall, math classes got the highest weighted mean of 4.50 which verbally described as very high.

Followed by English subject with a weighted mean of 3.63 which verbally described as high, while Science subject got the lowest weighted mean in terms of test anxiety with a mean of 3.54 which verbally described as high. Moreover, in terms of test anxiety, the statement refers to I am worried about making mistakes in our examination got the highest weighted mean of 4.81 which verbally described as very high, while the statement refers to I am usually not at ease during our examination got the highest mean of 3.82 which verbally described as high for English subject, and lastly the statement refers to I am afraid that my teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make got the highest weighted mean of 3.92 for Science subject. Test anxiety is a common occurrence among students of all ages and academic backgrounds. Studies have shown that as many as 16.4% of English secondary school pupils experience test anxiety. Because test anxiety can have a negative impact on academic achievement and subjective well-being, these prevalence percentages are worrisome (e.g., Steinmayr et al., 2016). Anxiety about tests is common in situations when achieving success is seen as a threat to one's self-worth (e.g., important exams). The concept of test anxiety is a multifaceted one (Pekrun, 2006).

Table 2. Class anxiety

Classes	Learners					
	Math		English		Science	
	WM	VD	WM	VD	WM	VD
I am tense and nervous in my class.	4.21	VH	3.69	H	3.14	N
During class, I find myself thinking about things that have nothing to do with the subject.	4.31	VH	3.57	H	3.18	N
I easily get so nervous in the subject.	4.01	H	3.46	H	3.34	N
Even if I am well prepared for class, I am still anxious	4.11	H	3.82	H	3.52	H
I often feel like not going to my class.	3.87	H	3.53	H	3.78	H
Weighted Mean	4.10	H	3.61	H	3.39	N

Table 2 shows the results in terms of learner's anxiety in terms of classes. Data shows that learners have a higher anxiety in math classes compared to English and science subjects. Overall, math classes got the highest weighted mean of 4.10 which verbally described as high. Followed by English subject with a weighted mean of 3.61 which also verbally described as high, while Science subject got the lowest weighted mean in terms of class anxiety with a mean of 3.39 which verbally described as neutral. Moreover, in terms of anxiety, the statement refers to during class, I find myself thinking about things that have nothing to do with the subject got the highest weighted mean for math subject, while the statement refers to even if I am well prepared for class, I feel anxious about it got the highest mean for English subject, and lastly the statement refers to I often feel like not going to my class got the highest weighted mean for science subject. This indicates that learners have different anxiety in terms of going to class. Human anxiety is a basic human feeling that comprises of dread and uncertainty, and develops when an individual feels the event is a threat to themselves or their self-esteem, according to Ajmal and Ahmad (2019). A person's anxiety can be classified as a state or a characteristic based on the length of time it lasts. Anxiety interferes with one's ability to think clearly. Students have difficulties in their academics and endure anxiety before tests or when faced with major life decisions. Anxiety has been shown to have a poor impact on students' academic performance, which in turn has a negative impact on the realization of critical cognitive and emotional objectives in distant learning education (Jegade, Alaiyemola, & Okebukola, 1990).

Table 3. Communication Anxiety

Communication anxiety	Learners					
	Math		English		Science	
	WM	VD	WM	VD	WM	VD
I get nervous and confused when I am communicate in class.	3.41	H	3.64	H	3.24	N
I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation.	4.28	VH	3.87	H	3.29	N
I am nervous speaking with my teacher.	4.26	VH	3.66	H	3.38	N
I am not confiden in class participation	4.08	H	3.43	H	3.51	H
I feel very self-conscious about speaking in front of other students	4.21	VH	3.78	H	3.28	N
Weighted Mean	4.04	H	3.68	H	3.34	N

Table 3 shows the results in terms of learner’s anxiety in terms of communication anxiety. Data shows that learners have also a higher anxiety in math classes compared to English and science subjects. Overall, math classes got the highest weighted mean of 4.04 which verbally described as high. Followed by English subject with a weighted mean of 3.68 which also verbally described as high, while Science subject got the lowest weighted mean in terms of class anxiety with a mean of 3.34 which verbally described as neutral. Moreover, in terms of anxiety, the statement refers to I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation got the highest weighted mean with 4.28 which verbally described as very high for math subject, while the statement refers to I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation got the highest mean of 3.87 which verbally described as high for english subject, and lastly the statement refers to I am not confiden in class participation got the highest weighted mean of 3.51 for Science subject. There is evidence to suggest that the ability to communicate effectively is not something that students are born with. In instances where they are the center of attention, such as when they have to address an audience, they experience emotions like dread and anxiety, resulting to nausea and perspiration. The majority of them strive to avoid circumstances in which they are required to perform or talk in front of an audience, but when they are forced to do so, they do so with a sense of dread and anxiety. This indicates that learners have different anxiety in terms of attending classes.

Table 4. Evaluation Anxiety

Evluation anxiety	Learners					
	Math		English		Science	
	WM	VD	WM	VD	WM	VD
I keep thinking that the other students are better at than I am.	4.08	H	3.82	H	4.09	H
It embarrasses me to volunteer answers in my class.	3.82	H	3.52	H	3.61	H
I get upset when I don’t understand what the teacher is correcting	4.21	VH	3.60	H	3.78	H
I can feel my heart pounding when I am going to be called in class.	3.78	H	3.87	H	3.92	H
Classes move so quickly, I worry about getting left behind.	4.02	H	4.01	H	4.05	H
Weighted Mean	3.98	H	3.76	H	3.89	H

Table 4 shows the results in terms of learner's anxiety in terms of evaluation anxiety. Data shows that learners have also a higher anxiety in math classes compared to English and science subjects. Overall, math classes got the highest weighted mean of 3.98 which verbally described as high. Followed by Science subject with a weighted mean of 3.89 which also verbally described as high, while English subject got the lowest weighted mean in terms of class anxiety with a mean of 3.76 which verbally described as high. Moreover, in terms of anxiety, the statement refers to I get upset when I don't understand what the teacher is correcting got the highest weighted mean with 4.21 which verbally described as very high for math subject, while the statement refers to I can feel my heart pounding when I am going to be called in class got the highest mean of 3.87 which verbally described as high for english subject, and lastly the statement refers to I keep thinking that the other students are better at than I am got the highest weighted mean of 4.09 for Science subject.

Previous studies have shown that anxiety levels vary within and across students, and are often measured by evaluating the severity and frequency of students' worried sensations (Spitzer et al., 2006). In college scientific classes, the Yerkes-Dodson law states that students may benefit from low levels of anxiety while being negatively affected by high levels of worry; student performance improves with anxiety, but levels of anxiety higher than a specific threshold negatively effect performance (Yerkes and Dodson, 1908). Anxiety, it has been shown, can boost a student's drive to succeed (Deshpande and Kawane, 1982). Students' general mental health and well-being can be improved by initiatives to lessen college student anxiety, which has been advocated for by both national and collegiate groups (Gallagher, 2014).

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Learners Profile and Learners Anxiety

Learners Anxiety	age	gender	Grade level	Parents Highest educational qualification
Test Anxiety	-.39	0.64	0.10*	0.52
Class Anxiety	0.78	0.48	0.47*	0.61
Communication Anxiety	0.55	-.62	0.64	0.58
Evaluation Anxiety	-.83	0.53	0.51	0.62

Data shows that there is a significant relationship between grade level and test (0.10) and class anxiety (0.47). The above table also shows that test and class anxiety are highly correlated with the grade level. This indicates that anxiety occurs in different grade level. Additionally, studies have shown that students suffer varying degrees of anxiety as they go up the academic ladder. Test anxiety will continue to be a major problem because of these claims. It is no wonder.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings, anxiety exist in every subject. While math subject was the most dominant form of anxiety provider due to its nature of solving problems with number, followed by english and science subject. Moreover, data showed that there is a need to strenghten the connection

between students and teachers in order to provide quality education. Hence, without genuine relationships and constant support of the teachers, learners develop different academic anxiety that leads to academic deficiency. By recognizing the impact of this results, it is very important to provide appropriate support to the learners.

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